

ANALYSIS OF THE EXISTING ASSIGNMENT ON ENGLISH SUBJECT AT ACADEMIC LYCEUM UNDER TASHKENT STATE UNIVERSITY OF ECONOMICS

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ABSTRACT

For a start, this article is aimed to analyze the assessment procedure at Academic lyceum under Tashkent State University of Economics with taken part of one student's learning process. Nunan (1989) claims that "learners may have a great influence on the effectiveness of the teaching and learning in unexpected ways. For example, a textbook or set of materials may be engaging at a suitable level, and supply necessary practice but not to be appreciated by learners, they fail to see any links between the book and the exams they are working toward." For these reasons, it is very essential to make some research under this issue and according to the results it is advisable to make some changes.

As we know, learners are the key participants in any kind of teaching process and it is significant to gather as many data as possible about their characteristics, language learning backgrounds, needs, deficiencies and others. The learner who studies at academic lyceum under Tashkent State University of Economics as a second year student is about 17 years old. She has been learning English since September in my GE (General English) class. She is learning English in the Pre-intermediate group now with 10 learners. She has a strong willing to learn English, because the following year she is going to enter one of the universities of Uzbekistan, and she intends to get an IELTS certificate by next year. She has not attended any English courses before, however she has enough capability of learning foreign

languages. In addition, she knows Russian language very well and she can speak Russian fluently, so it is not difficult to her to get some knowledge in English also. She is able to remember some new words, phrases in a quick way; she has an excellent pronunciation. Besides that, she is very punctual, responsible and she practices a lot on herself, does her lessons on time without delaying.

As I mentioned above, she studies at academic lyceum under Tashkent State University of Economics that is located in Chilanar district as a second year student. Due to the syllabus of the academic lyceum, she has English lessons 3times in a week. During the two term of the second course, students have overall 300 hours English lessons. Furthermore, they have to pass two kinds of mid-terms and two final

exams during the second year and students can be assessed by assessment for learning (**formative assessment**) due to their participations, activeness during the each class or they can be evaluated at the end of the unit or term via assessment of learning (**summative assessment**).

Nowadays, she is in the pre-intermediate level, before beginning the class she was taken a placement test of the education center per month ago. Due to the placement test, she worked on some reading comprehension tasks, such as open-ended, limited responses, selection (e.g., multiple-choice). And also she wrote an informal letter to her friend and she was taken speaking exam from various familiar learned topics, such as family relationship, food, friends, hobbies and leisure time activities and others which she has learned during a four-month English course. The aim of the placement tests is to place a student into a certain level, that's why this kind of placement tests are very beneficial and important in the development of the learners' knowledge of English, because they can have an opportunity to check their proficiency levels, capabilities, and deficiencies of language learning. Due to ideas of Brown (2010) "a learner's performance on the placement tests should illustrate the point at which the learner will find material neither too easy nor too difficult but appropriately challenging. A beneficial side of this test is to supply teachers with information about what may or may not need to be emphasized in teaching and learning period." Moreover, some achievement tests and proficiency tests can be applied as placement tests, because they aid to develop the classroom atmosphere. Furthermore, by being aware

of the lacks and needs of learners after the tests, teachers may have an explicit idea about how to get rid of the learners' deficiencies or what to teach more in order to fulfill the gaps that the learners expect and desire to enhance. The placement tests of the education center are held at the end of the each level encourage learners to do their best or to work better on themselves and they can be motivated by getting high results. It is very important and crucial if such kind of tests are used regularly in any kind of educational field, because they inspire both teachers and learners to reach desired competence or level of teaching and learning English and make them work a lot on their weak sides.

At academic lyceum under Tashkent State University of Economics, teachers conduct their lessons by using various themes and topics that are determined in the syllabus. During the each semester, students are required to prepare different independent works, Power Point presentations, group presentations, and they have to write different types of letters, essays, they have to work on various reading tasks, which relate to their learned topics. Besides that, they are taught how to enhance their speaking and listening proficiencies by practicing diverse assignments and exercises. At the end of the year 2, students have to achieve B1 level according to the curriculum. The students of the academic lyceum use the 2nd course "English Workbook" during their English class, this book was written by Bakiyeva G., Irisqulov A and other Uzbek experts in 2015. Second year students have two types of mid-term in each term. The second mid-term involves two parts itself. In the first part, students are required to write an essay

that consists of about 150-200 words on topic "Advantages and disadvantages of internet learning environment". Moreover, in the second part they have to demonstrate their oral skills via using PPT for the above-mentioned topic. Students are asked to prepare Power Point presentations in advance, because they have to show both their writing and speaking capabilities in the second mid-term.

In designing and creating any kind of assessment criteria, it is highly demanded to follow the five vital and major principles of assessment and testing, because it influence on the effectiveness of the work that can be done by the learners, and also it aids to make teachers' assessment process easier and more efficient. Grounlund (1998) states that "validity is the extent to which inferences made from assessment results are appropriate, meaningful and useful in terms of the purpose of the assessment". By following this idea, we can

say that the mid-term task is **valid**, since the students learn the principles of writing advantages and disadvantages essay in their classroom and it means that the material, which is taught in class, matches the material that is tested. However, the teachers do not provide students with clear instructions on what to do and how they can make some preparations for the mid-term task, there is no any explicit guideline that can help students to comprehend their task deeply. These factors affect the efficiency of learners' work and as a result, they will not be able to write better work in the exam. In addition to, the task is not so **reliable**, because it gives some clear directions only for evaluating PPT, but there is no any kind of rubrics for appraising written work and students are not aware how to get some marks for their piece of writing. This issue puts reliability under the threat and it leads to the decreasing students' success in writing skill.

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